

1 **hnRNPs are an integral component of the Xist RNP.**

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6 We demonstrate here that the heterogenous ribonucleoproteins (hnRNPs) including hnRNPD, hnRNPA0
7 and hnRNPU are an integral component of the Xist RNP. Proteomic RNA/protein interaction,
8 transcriptome co-regulation that identifies genes whose expression is most closely co-regulated with Xist
9 and recently identified Xist RNP components, and measurement of total transcription following genetic
10 modulation of DNA damage and repair pathway components that result in mobilization of the Xist RNP, an
11 RNP complex we continue to describe as a significant contributor to epigenetic gene regulation in
12 homeostasis and in transformation-associated epigenetic silencing, each support a central role for
13 hnRNPs as integral components of the Xist RNP.

14 **References**

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